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3 **High-pressure syntheses and crystal structure analyses of a new low-density CaFe_2O_4 -related**
4 **and CaTi_2O_4 -type MgAl_2O_4**

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14

15 **Abstract**

16 Phase transitions of MgAl₂O₄ spinel under lower mantle pressures remain unclear. In this study,
17 single crystals of CaTi₂O₄-type, CaFe₂O₄-type, and new low-density CaFe₂O₄-related MgAl₂O₄
18 were synthesized at 27 GPa and 2500 °C using a multi-anvil press. We also synthesized CaTi₂O₄-
19 type MgAl₂O₄ at 45 GPa and 1727 °C using multi-anvil technology that we developed with
20 tungsten carbide anvils. Structural analyses of CaTi₂O₄-type and low-density CaFe₂O₄-related
21 MgAl₂O₄ were performed using single crystal X-ray diffraction. The lattice parameters of the
22 CaTi₂O₄-type phases synthesized at 27 GPa and 45 GPa were determined to be $a = 2.7903(4) \text{ \AA}$, b
23 $= 9.2132(10) \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 9.3968(12) \text{ \AA}$ and $a = 2.7982(6) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 9.2532(15) \text{ \AA}$, and $c = 9.4461(16)$
24 \AA , respectively, ($Z = 4$, space group: *Cmcm*). The refined structures had an AlO₆ octahedral site
25 and a MgO₈ bicapped trigonal prism with two longer cation-oxygen bonds. The low-density
26 CaFe₂O₄-related phase had a novel structure with orthorhombic symmetry (space group: *Pnma*),
27 and the lattice parameters were determined to be $a = 9.207(2) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.0118(6) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9.739(2) \text{ \AA}$,
28 and $Z = 4$. The structural framework comprised tunnel-shaped spaces constructed by edge- and
29 corner-sharing of AlO₆ and a 4+1 AlO₅ trigonal bipyramid, in which MgO₅ trigonal bipyramids
30 were accommodated. CaFe₂O₄-type MgAl₂O₄ also had the same space group of *Pnma* but a slightly
31 different atomic arrangement, with Mg and Al coordination numbers of 8 and 6, respectively. The
32 low-density CaFe₂O₄-related phase had the smallest density (3.50 g/cm³) in MgAl₂O₄ polymorphs,

33 despite high-pressure synthesis from the spinel-type phase (3.58 g/cm^3). This result indicates that
34 the low-density CaFe_2O_4 -related phase was formed via back-transformation from a high-pressure
35 form during the recovery. The present study, combined with the previously determined phase
36 relations, demonstrated that the phase transition between CaFe_2O_4 - and CaTi_2O_4 -type MgAl_2O_4
37 had a steep Clapeyron slope. The findings suggest that the CaTi_2O_4 -type phase may be stable in
38 basaltic and continental crusts in a wide lower-mantle pressure range at higher temperatures than
39 the average mantle geotherm. The low-density CaFe_2O_4 -related phase also may be found in
40 shocked meteorites and play an important role as a possible indicator for the shock conditions.

41

42 **Keywords**

43 Single-crystal structure analysis, high pressure, phase transition, spinel, post-spinel, calcium
44 titanate, calcium ferrite

45

1. Introduction

46

47 MgAl₂O₄ spinel (Sp) is a minor but common mineral in lherzolite xenoliths from 20–50
48 km depths and in meteorites. The high-pressure polymorphs of MgAl₂O₄ with calcium ferrite (CF)-
49 and calcium titanate (CT)-type structures are considered important and abundant components that
50 are stable under lower-mantle conditions in Al₂O₃-rich rocks, such as basalt, upper continental
51 crust, and sediment (e.g., Irifune et al. 1994; Ono et al. 2005; Ishii et al. 2012, 2019). High-pressure
52 transitions in MgAl₂O₄ thus have been an important subject for understanding hosts of aluminum
53 in the Earth's mantle.

54 High-pressure and high-temperature phase transitions in MgAl₂O₄ have been investigated
55 for more than four decades (Liu 1978; Irifune et al. 1991; Funamori et al. 1998; Akaogi et al. 1999;
56 Irifune et al. 2002; Ono et al. 2006; Enomoto et al. 2009; Kojitani et al. 2010; Kojitani et al. 2012).
57 At temperatures of 1200 to 1600 °C with pressures of 15 to 16 GPa, MgAl₂O₄ Sp decomposes to
58 MgO periclase (Pc) + Al₂O₃ corundum (Cor) at pressures of 15 to 16 GPa. It reacts at pressures of
59 25 to 27 GPa to form CF-type MgAl₂O₄ (Akaogi et al. 1999; Irifune et al. 2002; Kojitani et al.
60 2012). At temperatures above 2000 °C and pressures of 20 to 26 GPa, Sp first dissociates to
61 modified ludwigite-type Mg₂Al₂O₅ + Cor. The dissociated phases again form a single phase with
62 MgAl₂O₄ composition at pressures above 26 GPa, and this single phase has been recovered as an
63 unknown phase in ambient conditions (Enomoto et al. 2009; Kojitani et al. 2010). Above 40 GPa,

64 the CF phase transforms to a CT-type phase in a wide temperature range of 1200 to 3000 °C
65 (Funamori et al. 1998; Ono et al. 2006). This phase is poorly characterized but believed to have an
66 orthorhombic structure, which is referred to as ϵ -MgAl₂O₄. This phase may be stable between 25
67 and 50 GPa at 1100–2500 °C (Liu 1978; Ono et al. 2006). Enomoto et al. (2009) showed that the
68 powder X-ray diffraction pattern of the MgAl₂O₄ unknown phase in ambient conditions differs
69 from that of any known MgAl₂O₄ phase, including ϵ -MgAl₂O₄. Thus, stabilities and structures of
70 ϵ -MgAl₂O₄ and Enomoto et al.'s (2009) unknown phase are under debate.

71 In this study, we synthesized single crystals of CT-type, CF-type, and new low-density
72 CF-related (LD-CF) MgAl₂O₄ at 27 GPa and 2500 °C in a single run. The pressure and temperature
73 conditions were identical to those from which Enomoto et al. (2009) recovered the unknown phase.
74 We also synthesized CT-type MgAl₂O₄ at 45 GPa and 1727 °C using a multi-anvil technique that
75 we developed. We examined structures of the CT-type and the LD-CF phases of MgAl₂O₄ using
76 single-crystal X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis. We also assessed the stability of these phases in
77 the deep mantle and shocked meteorites.

78 **2. Experimental methods**

79 **2.1. High-pressure and high-temperature experiment at 27 GPa and 2500 °C**

80 Synthetic MgAl₂O₄ Sp was used as a starting material, which was synthesized from a
81 mixture of MgO + Al₂O₃ with a molar ratio of 1:1 by heating at 1500 °C for 24 h. The high-pressure

82 and high-temperature synthesis was performed using a Kawai-type multi-anvil high-pressure
83 apparatus at the Department of Chemistry, Gakushuin University, in Japan. Tungsten carbide (WC)
84 anvils with 2.5-mm truncated edge lengths (Grade TF05, produced by Fuji Die Co., Ltd.) were
85 used in combination with a 5 wt% Cr₂O₃-doped MgO octahedral pressure medium with a 7-mm
86 edge length. A cylindrical Re heater was put at the center of the pressure medium. The starting
87 material was put directly in the central part of the heater. A LaCrO₃ sleeve was placed outside the
88 heater, with lids placed at both ends in the heater. Re disks were placed at the boundaries between
89 the LaCrO₃ lids and sample to avoid contamination. The sample pressure was estimated based on
90 a pressure calibration curve at 1600–1800 °C (Ishii et al. 2011, 2012), in which the temperature
91 effect on pressure was neglected. Temperature was measured at the central part of the outer surface
92 of the heater using a Pt/Pt-13%Rh thermocouple up to 1800 °C. We estimated a sample temperature
93 of 2500 °C by extrapolation of the power-temperature relationships up to 1800 °C. No pressure
94 effect on electromotive force of the thermocouple was corrected.

95 The sample was compressed to a target pressure at an almost constant rate of 1 MN/h at
96 room temperature and then heated to the target temperature of 2500 °C at a rate of 100 °C/min.
97 After keeping this temperature for 5 min, the sample was quenched by turning electrical power off
98 and slowly decompressed to ambient pressure for 12 hours. Colorless and light-green single

99 crystals in the run product (see sections 2.3 and 2.4 for details) were picked up for chemical-
100 composition and structural analyses.

101 **2.2. High-pressure and high-temperature experiment at 45 GPa and 1727 °C**

102 The high-pressure and high-temperature experiment was conducted using the Kawai-type
103 multi-anvil apparatus with the Osugi-type guide block system, which was referred to as DIA-type¹
104 (IRIS-15) (Ishii et al. 2016, 2019) and installed at the Bayerisches Geoinstitut, University of
105 Bayreuth. TF05 WC anvils with 1°-tapering and 1.5-mm truncation were adopted in combination
106 with a 5.7-mm Cr-doped MgO pressure medium. The tapering technique in combination with hard
107 WC anvils allows generation of pressures higher than 40 GPa, even using WC anvils (Ishii et al.
108 2016, 2017a, 2017b; Liu et al. 2017a). An Re foil heater was put at the center of the pressure
109 medium. A ZrO₂ thermal insulator was located outside the heater. Mo electrodes at both ends of
110 the heater were connected with the WC anvils. A dense alumina tube (outer/inner diameter = 0.5
111 mm/0.3 mm; height = 2.1 mm) was inserted into the heater. A mixture of MgO-Mg(OH)₂-SiO₂-
112 Al(OH)₃-⁵⁷Fe₂O₃ was packed in a gold tube capsule. The capsule was put inside the alumina tube,

¹ This guide block system was first devised by Jiro Osugi's laboratory in the Department of Chemistry, Kyoto University. The system comprises upper and lower guide blocks, with four 45° slopes and four sliding wedges on the guide blocks. Each guide block and sliding wedge is equipped with an anvil. The six anvils in the [100] directions synchronously compress a cubic space via uniaxial force.

113 with MgO lids located at both ends. A W-3%Re/W-25%Re thermocouple measured the surface
114 temperature of the heater.

115 The cell assembly was compressed to the maximum press load of 15 MN for 5 h and then
116 heated to the target temperature of 1727 °C. After 2 h, the assembly was quenched by turning off
117 electric power, and then the pressure was released for 15 hours. The generated pressure was
118 estimated based on results of pressure calibration with separate runs, which suggested a sample
119 pressure of 45 GPa at a press load of 15 MN and a temperature of 1727 °C, based on alumina
120 solubility in MgSiO₃ bridgmanite (Liu et al. 2017b; Ishii et al. 2016, 2017b). After recovering, we
121 found a light-green crystal inside the heater, which was picked up for analyses of its composition
122 and crystal structure.

123 **2.3. Sample characterization**

124 Phases of the starting material of MgAl₂O₄ Sp were identified using a powder X-ray
125 diffractometer (Rigaku RINT 2500V) with monochromatized Cr K α radiation operated at 45 kV
126 and 250 mA. Compositions of crystals obtained by the high-pressure and high-temperature
127 syntheses were analyzed using an electron microprobe analyzer (EPMA) with wavelength-
128 dispersive spectrometers (JEOL, JXA-8200). Compositional data were collected at an accelerated
129 voltage and probe current of 15 kV and 10 nA, respectively, for 20 sec on the peaks of Mg and Al
130 and 10 sec on the background. Natural pyrope was used as the standard material for Mg and Al.

131 The compositions of the colorless and light-green crystals synthesized at 27 GPa were Mg:Al =
132 0.998(5):2.000(3) and Mg:Al = 0.995(5):2.002(2), respectively. Origin of the light-green color
133 may be due to chromium impurities from the LaCrO₃ thermal insulator or rhenium impurities from
134 the Re heater, because crystals of this color generally were found near the heater. However, these
135 elements were undetectable by EPMA analysis, and these impurities did not affect the single-
136 crystal analyses.

137 The light-green crystal synthesized at 45 GPa had a composition of Mg:Al = 1.07(2):
138 1.94(2), although the capsule with MgO-Al₂O₃-Fe₂O₃-SiO₂-H₂O compositional powder was put at
139 the center of the assembly. Fe, Al-bearing bridgmanite was found in the capsule. The composition
140 of the crystal thus may indicate that the crystal was formed by a reaction between the alumina tube
141 and magnesia lids outside the capsule (see section 2.2). We were unable to determine the location
142 of the light-green crystal due to a large deformation of the capsule. The color may be due to trace
143 amounts of Fe in the sample that were introduced when the gold capsule was broken.

144 **2.4. Single crystal X-ray structure analysis**

145 The structures of recovered crystals were analyzed using single-crystal X-ray
146 diffractometers. Table 1 summarizes the crystallographic data of the crystals, including reliability
147 factors (R_{int} , R_1 , and wR_2) and goodness-of-fit indicators (S_{fit}).

148 **2.4.1. New low-density CaFe₂O₄-related MgAl₂O₄.** A colorless, single crystal of LD-CF

149 MgAl₂O₄, approximately 50×50×50 μm³ in size, was used for the single crystal XRD measurement.
150 The data were collected using a single-crystal X-ray diffractometer (Bruker AXS, Smart APEX2)
151 at Gakushuin University. The diffractometer used a charge-coupled device detector in the 2θ range,
152 up to 57.18°, with Mo Kα radiation from a rotating anode at a voltage of 50 kV and current of 240
153 mA. The WinGX program (Farrugia 2012) was employed for calculations of space group
154 assignment and structure refinement. The systematic absences (*h* odd for *hk0*; *k* + *l* odd for *0kl*;
155 and *h*, *k*, and *l* odd for *h00*, *k00*, and *l00*, respectively) were observed, indicating that the space
156 group was *Pnma* or *Pn2₁a*. The *N*(*Z*) test for a center of symmetry (Hargreaves and Gogoi 1966)
157 showed the centrosymmetric space group of *Pnma*. Absorption correction was empirically made
158 using the SADABS program (Sheldrick 1996), resulting in a discrepancy factor among equivalent
159 reflections (*R*_{int}) of 2.65%.

160 The initial structure for the refinement was found using the direct method of the SHELXL-
161 97 program (Sheldrick 1997). Refinement of the structure was performed against $|F|^2$ using the
162 full-matrix least-squares method with the scattering factors of neutral atoms (International Tables
163 for Crystallography 1992). At the initial stage of the refinement, the isotropic displacement factors
164 of all atoms were refined with the atomic positions. The site occupancies of Mg and Al in each site
165 were examined, and no disordering gave the lowest values of the reliability factors *R*₁ and *wR*₂,
166 indicating no disordering in any site. At the final stage, the anisotropic displacement factors were

167 refined with all independent parameters simultaneously.

168 **2.4.2. CaTi₂O₄-type MgAl₂O₄.** Light-green single crystals of CT-type MgAl₂O₄
169 (approximately 30×30×10 μm³ and 40×40×20 μm³ in size and synthesized at 27 GPa and 45 GPa,
170 respectively) were used for single-crystal data collection. Single-crystal XRD was conducted using
171 a 3-circle Bruker diffractometer equipped with a SMART APEX CCD detector and Incoatec IμS
172 3.0 microfocus X-ray source (Ag-Kα radiation) at Bayerisches Geoinstitut, University of Bayreuth.
173 Processing of XRD data (unit cell determination and integration of reflection intensities) was
174 performed using CrysAlisPro software (Rigaku Oxford Diffraction 2019). Systematic absences
175 characteristic of *C*-centering ($h + k$ odd for all reflections) were observed. Empirical absorption
176 correction was applied using spherical harmonics and implemented in the SCALE3 ABSPACK
177 scaling algorithm, which is included in the CrysAlisPro software.

178 The processed XRD data showed R_{int} values of 3.92% and 2.82% for crystals recovered
179 from 27 GPa and 45 GPa, respectively. The crystal structures were determined using the dual-
180 space method in the SHELXT software. After the structure was determined, most atoms were
181 found, and the remaining atoms were located from a series of difference Fourier map cycles. The
182 crystal structures were refined in anisotropic approximation for all atoms against F^2 on all data
183 using the full-matrix least squares method in the SHELXL software. For the 45-GPa crystal, we
184 assumed MgAl₂O₄ composition, although the composition was not stoichiometric, as previously

185 mentioned. The difference between the scattering factors of Mg and Al was very small, and the
186 mosaicity of the crystal was greater than the other samples. The observed high-mosaicity caused
187 the diffraction peak profiles to broaden at high 2θ , limiting the resolution of the structure
188 refinement.

189 3. Results

190 Figures 1 and 2 show the crystal structures of the LD-CF and CT phases of MgAl_2O_4 in
191 this study. Table 2 summarizes the refined structural parameters for both phases. Table 3 shows the
192 interatomic distances and angles for the phases. In the sample synthesized at 27 GPa and 2500 °C,
193 we also identified single-crystal grains with a unit cell ($a = 8.6565(13) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 2.7891(9) \text{ \AA}$, $c =$
194 $9.9509(19) \text{ \AA}$, $V = 240.25(10) \text{ \AA}^3$) different from those belonging to the CT and LD-CF phases,
195 which were picked up from the bottom part of the heater. Analysis of systematic absences in terms
196 of lattice-centering suggests the *Pnma* space group. Unfortunately, the data quality was not
197 sufficient for accurate refinement of the crystal structure. Assuming that the space group and values
198 of the unit cell parameters agree with previously reported values for CF-type MgAl_2O_4 , however,
199 we concluded that our sample contains some CF-type MgAl_2O_4 .

200 3.1. Crystal structure of new low-density CaFe_2O_4 -related MgAl_2O_4

201 The XRD measurement showed that new LD-CF MgAl_2O_4 had lattice parameters of $a =$
202 $9.207(2) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.0118(6) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 9.739(2) \text{ \AA}$, and $V = 270.06(10) \text{ \AA}^3$ with the space group of *Pnma*.

203 The determined structure, shown in Figure 1, had one trigonal bipyramid site for a magnesium
204 cation (MgO_5) and two crystallographically independent polyhedral sites for aluminum cations
205 (Al1O_6 and $4+1 \text{ Al2O}_5$). The equivalent aluminum-oxygen polyhedra of Al1O_{10} and Al2O_8 formed
206 one-dimensional structures by edge-sharing double chains running parallel to the b axis (Figure 1).
207 The four double chains made an aluminum-oxygen polyhedral framework by corner-sharing with
208 each other. The magnesium cation was accommodated in the five-oxygen coordinated site in a
209 tunnel-shaped space formed in the framework. The average Al-O distances of the Al1O_6 and Al2O_5
210 polyhedra were 1.952 Å and 1.860 Å, respectively, which were close to the sum of the effective
211 ionic radii of aluminum and oxygen, 1.935 Å and 1.88 Å, calculated from $^{\text{VI}}\text{Al}^{3+}$ (0.535 Å), $^{\text{V}}\text{Al}^{3+}$
212 (0.48 Å), and $^{\text{VI}}\text{O}^{2-}$ (1.40 Å). The average Mg-O distance in MgO_5 , 2.031 Å, was nearly the same
213 value as the sum of the effective ion radii of $^{\text{V}}\text{Mg}^{2+}$ (0.66 Å) + $^{\text{VI}}\text{O}^{2-}$, 2.06 Å. The effective
214 coordination numbers (n_c) (Nespolo et al. 2001) of Mg and Al1, calculated using cation-five and -
215 six neighboring oxygen bonds, were 4.72 and 5.98, respectively, indicating that those coordination
216 environments were suitable for the cations.

217 The n_c value of Al2 (4.23) was near four. The atomic distance of Al2-O4 (2.161 Å) was
218 0.3–0.4 Å longer than the other bonds, and the position of Al2 in the oxygen-trigonal bipyramid
219 site was relatively off-centered, implying that 4 coordination was plausible for Al2 (the oxygen-
220 tetrahedral site). The n_c value of Al2 in the oxygen tetrahedral site was 3.98, which was not

221 significantly different from that in the oxygen-trigonal bipyramid site. This phase was closely
222 related to the CF-type structure, which is based on similar atomic arrangement and identical
223 symmetry but extremely low density. In this paper, we therefore call this a “low-density CF-related”
224 phase, although the CT-type phase also had similar features. We emphasize that only a few
225 compounds that have Mg or Al in the 5 coordination (trigonal bipyramid) have been found, to the
226 best of our knowledge, including Al_2SiO_5 andalusite with AlO_6 and AlO_5 polyhedra (Taylor 1929)
227 and $\text{Mg}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ with MgO_6 and MgO_5 polyhedra (Nord and Kierkegaard 1968).

228 **3.2. Crystal structure of CaTi_2O_4 -type MgAl_2O_4**

229 According to results of the XRD measurements, the MgAl_2O_4 phases synthesized at 27
230 GPa and 2500 °C had the orthorhombic space group $Cmcm$, with lattice parameters of $a =$
231 $2.7903(4)$ Å, $b = 9.2132(10)$ Å, and $c = 9.3968(12)$ Å and a unit-cell volume of $V = 241.57(5)$ Å³.
232 The $Cmcm$ - MgAl_2O_4 phase adopted the structural type of CaTi_2O_4 (CT) (Figure 2). Mg^{2+} cations
233 surrounded by 6 oxygen atoms formed a distorted trigonal prism with Mg-O distances of $2.018(3)$
234 and $2.207(2)$ Å. Two additional oxygen atoms in the distance of $2.5607(7)$ Å completed 8-fold
235 bipolar prismatic coordination for Mg. The prisms connected through the common triangular faces
236 formed rods parallel to the a axis. Al^{3+} cations had octahedral coordination using 6 oxygen atoms,
237 and Al-O distances varied from $1.8468(17)$ to $1.9858(7)$ Å. The octahedra connected through

238 shared edges to form chains parallel to the a axis. The MgO_8 polyhedra and AlO_6 octahedra were
239 connected via common edges and corners.

240 We also obtained XRD data from the crystal synthesized at 45 GPa and 1727 °C, showing
241 the CT-type structure with lattice parameters of $a = 2.7982(6)$ Å, $b = 9.2532(15)$ Å, $c = 9.4461(16)$
242 Å, and $V = 244.58(8)$ Å³. The volume was ~ 3 Å³ larger than that synthesized at 27 GPa. This
243 difference may be due to higher Mg content ($\text{Al/Mg}=1.81$) for the 45-GPa crystal than that for the
244 27-GPa crystal ($\text{Al/Mg}=2$), which would require large Mg atoms to partially occupy the smaller
245 octahedral Al-site. The average bond length of AlO_6 octahedra (1.936 Å) was larger than that in
246 the 27-GPa crystal (1.928 Å), supporting incorporation of Mg into the octahedral site. Based on
247 the chemical composition analysis, this crystal may have oxygen vacancy or hydrogen in the
248 structure due to its inconsistent charge balance (cation: +7.96; oxygen: -8). However, it was
249 difficult to further discuss these possibilities due to the limited amount of sample and relatively
250 poor quality of EPMA data.

251 **4. Discussion**

252 **4.1. High-pressure crystal chemistry of MgAl_2O_4 polymorphs**

253 The new LD-CF MgAl_2O_4 has a structure similar to CF- and CT-type MgAl_2O_4 , but it has
254 not been described previously. Figure 3 compares the structures of MgAl_2O_4 polymorphs. CF- and
255 CT-type structures consist of double chains of edge-shared AlO_6 octahedra running parallel to an

256 orthorhombic cell axis. Both structures are classified by differences in the AlO_6 -octahedral
257 frameworks (Decker et al. 1957; Rogge et al. 1998; Yamanaka et al. 2009; Ishii et al. 2014, 2015,
258 2018). In the CF-type structure, an Mg cation occupies a tunnel-shaped space formed by corner-
259 sharing of the four double chains, making 8-oxygen coordination for Mg in an oxygen-trigonal
260 prism site with two longer Mg-oxygen bonds. The CT-type structure also makes a tunnel-shape
261 space by corner- and edge-sharing of the four double chains, making a mirror plane parallel to the
262 tunnel direction (Figure 2). In addition, the structure of CT-type has two much longer Mg-oxygen
263 bonds than those of the CF-type structure, making 6 coordination practical for Mg.

264 In the LD-CF structure, the coordination numbers of Al2 (4+1 coordination) and Mg (5
265 coordination) are lower than those in CF- and CT-type MgAl_2O_4 (6 coordination for Al and 6+2 or
266 8 coordination for Mg, respectively). The coordination number for Al is even smaller than the 6
267 coordination of the ambient pressure phase of MgAl_2O_4 Sp (Meducin et al. 2004). Table 4 shows
268 molar volumes and densities of the phases with MgAl_2O_4 composition. The LD-CF phase has the
269 smallest density among these phases, even though this phase was recovered from a higher-pressure
270 side than the stability field of $\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_5 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (20–25 GPa and 2000–2500°C), in which Al was
271 accommodated in oxygen-octahedral sites. These facts indicate that the LD-CF structure is of a
272 metastable phase formed during quench and decompression processes of a stable phase at high
273 pressure and high temperature. This kind of back-transformation has been reported in several

274 compounds, such as the perovskite–LiNbO₃-type transition in FeTiO₃, MgSiO₃-Al₂O₃, and
275 MgSiO₃-FeAlO₃ systems and CF-modified CF transition in FeCr₂O₄ (Leinenweber et al. 1991;
276 Akaogi et al. 2017; Ishii et al. 2014, 2017b; Liu et al. 2017b, 2019, 2020).

277 Our recent study reported a newly structured MgFe₂O₄ high-pressure phase, which was
278 also interpreted as a back-transformed phase. This MgFe₂O₄ phase has a “Z-shape” framework
279 consisting of edge-sharing (Mg,Fe)O₆ octahedra with one (Mg,Fe)O₄ tetrahedral and two
280 (Mg,Fe)O₆ octahedral sites in the framework (Ishii et al. 2020), which differs from the LD-CF
281 MgAl₂O₄. We emphasize that to the best of our knowledge, the LD-CF MgAl₂O₄ is the first case
282 indicating the back-transformed phase has lower density than the ambient pressure phase. It is
283 suggested that high-pressure crystal chemistry in AB₂O₄ is much more complicated than previously
284 considered. The back-transformation from a high-pressure phase could be a distinct method to
285 design novel compounds and useful for understanding high-pressure crystal chemistry.

286 Ishii et al. (2018) classified quenchable CF- and CT-type phases in AB₂O₄ compositions
287 using ionic radii of *A* and *B* sites, showing the CT-type phase at the *B/A* ionic radius ratio around
288 0.7. In this classification, MgAl₂O₄ is categorized as the CF-type (*B/A* ionic radius ratio = 0.6).
289 They posited that quenchable CT-type MgAl₂O₄ may be due to an Mg-Al disorder between the *A*-
290 and *B*-sites or a different *B/A* ionic radius ratio at high pressures. Our structural analysis of CT-
291 type MgAl₂O₄ shows no disordering between the *A*- and *B*-sites, implying that the CT-type phase

292 should stabilize due to an increase of the B/A ionic radius ratio under high pressures.
293 Compressibilities of A - and B -sites in the CT-type phase will provide more information to
294 understand this issue and to improve the categorization. We emphasize that MgAl_2O_4 Sp is only a
295 single compound whose high-pressure phases-with both the CF- and CT-types are quenchable.

296 **4.2. Phase stabilities of MgAl_2O_4 high-pressure polymorphs**

297 Enomoto et al. (2009) reported phase relations in MgAl_2O_4 up to 27 GPa and 2500 °C and
298 found an unknown phase with an MgAl_2O_4 composition in the run products recovered from 25.5–
299 27 GPa and 2100–2500 °C. The pressure and temperature conditions under which we synthesized
300 the LD-CF phase (27 GPa and 2500 °C) fall within the region where the unknown phase was
301 synthesized by Enomoto et al. (2009). Furthermore, several strong diffraction peaks of the
302 unknown phase in the powder XRD data observed by Enomoto et al. (2009) agree with the
303 diffraction peaks of the present LD-CF phase. For example, d -values of 4.8691 Å, 3.3442 Å,
304 2.6518 Å, and 2.5207 Å with relatively high intensities, as reported in Enomoto et al. (2009),
305 correspond to diffractions with indexes of 002, 202, 203, and 210, respectively, in the present LD-
306 CF phase. This agreement indicates that the unknown phase reported by Enomoto et al. (2009) is
307 LD-CF MgAl_2O_4 . The fact that we synthesized the CF-type and CT-type phases together with the
308 LD-CF phase indicates that LD-CF MgAl_2O_4 might be back-transformed from either of these high-
309 pressure phases with an MgAl_2O_4 composition. Previous studies reported that ϵ - MgAl_2O_4 , which

310 is stable between 25 and 50 GPa (Liu 1978; Ono et al. 2006), is a candidate for the phase under
311 high pressure and high temperature, but its detailed structure remains unclear. A further study with
312 in situ X-ray observation under high pressure and high temperature is needed to reveal a high-
313 pressure phase to produce the LD-CF MgAl₂O₄ during recovery.

314 As shown in Table 4, our study indicated that the CT-type phase had a density of 3.864–
315 3.912 g/cm³ at ambient conditions, which is lower than the 3.933–3.937 g/cm³ of the CF-type
316 phase given by Kojitani et al. (2007) and this study. The CT-type MgAl₂O₄ by Ono et al. (2006)
317 also has a smaller density of 3.927(3) g/cm³ than that of the CF-type phase. The in situ X-ray
318 diffraction experiments at 45–117 GPa and 1200–2500°C, however, indicated that the CT-type
319 phase is a higher-pressure phase than the CF-type phase (Ono et al. 2006). On the contrary, the
320 coordination number of Mg atoms in the CF-type phase is higher than that of the CT-type phase,
321 which suggests that the CF-type phase may be a higher-density phase, at least in ambient
322 conditions. One explanation for this contradiction is a compressibility difference between the CF-
323 type and CT-type phases.

324 The bulk moduli of CF- and CT-type MgAl₂O₄, reported as 210–241 GPa and 210–219
325 GPa, respectively (Yutani et al. 1997; Funamori et al. 1998; Irifune et al. 2002; Ono et al. 2006),
326 are currently indistinguishable within the errors, however. We nevertheless consider that the *c*-axis
327 may shrink more efficiently in the CT-type structure than the other directions, because the link of

328 double chains is edge-sharing in the *b*-axis direction but corner-sharing in the *c*-direction, making
329 the structure more flexible in the *c*-axis (Siersch et al. 2017; Ishii et al. 2017). This possible
330 preferred shrinkage by compression would make a higher coordination number for *A*-site cation
331 and a density crossover between the two phases. Another possible explanation is the difference in
332 thermal expansivity of CF- and CT-type MgAl₂O₄, which has not yet been constrained
333 experimentally. Compression experiments at high temperatures of CF- and CT-type MgAl₂O₄ will
334 clarify any contradictions in the density difference between CF-type and CT-type phases.

335 **5. Implications**

336 **5.1. Shocked meteorites and impact craters**

337 LD-CF MgAl₂O₄ is a completely new, structured phase that was synthesized at 27 GPa
338 and 2500 °C. It was certainly formed via back-transformation from a high-pressure phase, as
339 previously mentioned. Shocked meteorites and impact craters bring high-pressure phases in the
340 shock events. These high-pressure phases provide important clues about pressure-temperature
341 conditions in shock events. MgAl₂O₄ spinel is found in stony meteorites as a minor mineral, and
342 therefore, LD-CF MgAl₂O₄ formed by a shock event is expected to be found in shocked meteorites
343 and impact craters. It thus may play an important role as a possible indicator for shock conditions
344 of 26–27 GPa and 2100–2500 °C.

345 **5.2. Mineralogy in the deep mantle**

346 We demonstrated that CT-type MgAl_2O_4 is stable even at 27 GPa and temperatures higher
347 than 2000 °C. The results, together with the present observation that the CT-type phase was located
348 near the heater at 27 GPa and 2500 °C, indicate that the CT-type phase is a high-temperature phase
349 of the CF-type. The present 45-GPa synthesis of the CT phase, along with previous studies
350 (Funamori et al. 1998; Ono et al. 2006), suggest that the CT phase is stable at pressures higher than
351 40 GPa. In the system FeCr_2O_4 , the CF-CT phase transition boundary has a steep negative
352 Clapeyron slope of about ~ 100 MPa/K (Ishii et al. 2014). This steep slope originates from a small
353 volume change between the CF and CT phases, which can cause the large dP/dT ($=\Delta S/\Delta V$) value.
354 It is therefore likely that the CF-CT phase transition boundary in the MgAl_2O_4 system also has a
355 steep dP/dT slope due to the small volume difference between the CF and CT phases (Table 4).

356 Ono et al. (2005) synthesized the CT phase in a basaltic crust composition at 143 GPa,
357 which is higher than the core-mantle boundary pressure. This finding may indicate that the CT
358 phase is stable around the bottom of the core-mantle boundary. If the steep negative boundary is
359 common to CF–CT transitions, the CT phase may be stable at high temperatures, such as those
360 found in upwelling plumes with basaltic and continental-crust compositions in the lower mantle
361 (Ricolleau et al. 2010; Ishii et al. 2012, 2019). Thus, it is valuable for better understanding of the

362 mantle structure and dynamics to investigate the stability of CT phases with more realistic
363 compositions in the lower mantle and in a wide temperature range.

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372

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515 **Figure captions**

(A)

(B)

516

517 Figure 1. The refined structure of low-density CaFe₂O₄-related MgAl₂O₄, revealed by single-crystal X-

518 ray diffraction analysis. (a) Crystal structure viewed from the *b* axis. A solid rectangular box shows the

519 unit cell. (b) Detailed coordination environments of each site. Red spheres are oxygen atoms.

520

521

522

523 Figure 2. The refined structure of CaTi₂O₄-type MgAl₂O₄ synthesized at 27 GPa and 2500 °C, revealed
524 by single-crystal X-ray diffraction analysis. (a) Crystal structure viewed from the *a* axis. A solid
525 rectangular box shows the unit cell. (b) Detailed coordination environments of each site. Red spheres are
526 oxygen atoms.

527

528 Figure 3. Structural comparison among MgAl_2O_4 compounds at ambient conditions. The numbers below

529 the structures are coordination numbers for Mg and Al. Dashed lines are the longest oxygen-cation bonds

530 in the polyhedra, which contributed less to the coordination of the cations. Blue octahedra and yellow

531 trigonal bipyramids accommodate Al cations. Orange spheres are Mg cations. In the Sp (spinel) phase,

532 Mg cations are accommodated in tetrahedral sites. Red spheres are oxygen atoms. Solid lines are unit cells.

533 CF: calcium ferrite, CT: calcium titanate, LD-CF: low-density calcium ferrite-related.

534 Table 1. Crystallographic data of new low-density CaFe₂O₄-related and CaTi₂O₄-type MgAl₂O₄

Crystal structure	Low-density CaFe ₂ O ₄ -related	^a CaTi ₂ O ₄ -type	^b CaTi ₂ O ₄ -type
Crystal color	Colorless	Light green	Light green
Crystal system	Orthorhombic	Orthorhombic	Orthorhombic
Lattice parameter	$a = 9.207(2) \text{ \AA}$	$a = 2.7903(4) \text{ \AA}$	$a = 2.7982(6) \text{ \AA}$
	$b = 3.0118(6) \text{ \AA}$	$b = 9.2132(10) \text{ \AA}$	$b = 9.2532(15) \text{ \AA}$
	$c = 9.739(2) \text{ \AA}$	$c = 9.3968(12) \text{ \AA}$	$c = 9.4461(16) \text{ \AA}$
	$V = 270.06(10) \text{ \AA}^3$	$V = 241.57(5) \text{ \AA}^3$	$V = 244.58(8) \text{ \AA}^3$
Z	4	4	4
Space group	<i>Pnma</i> (no. 62)	<i>Cmcm</i> (no. 63)	<i>Cmcm</i> (no. 63)
Measurement temperature	298 K	298 K	298 K
Measured/unique reflections	2378/384	1458/368	786/160
Unique reflections with $F_o > 4\sigma$	327	313	^c 160
Index ranges	$-11 \leq h \leq 12$	$-2 \leq h \leq 4$	$-3 \leq h \leq 4$
	$-3 \leq k \leq 4$	$-15 \leq k \leq 14$	$-12 \leq k \leq 12$
	$-12 \leq l \leq 12$	$-15 \leq l \leq 16$	$-9 \leq l \leq 13$
2θ max	57.18°	57.044°	47.42°
R_{int}	0.0265	0.0392	0.0282
$R1 (F_o > 4\sigma (F_o))$	0.024	0.0499	0.0425
$R1$ (all data)	0.0309	0.0615	0.0425
$wR2$ (all)	0.0716	0.1174	0.0952
Goodness-of-fit (S_{fit})	1.187	1.245	1.211

535 $R_{\text{int}} = \Sigma | |F_o|^2 - |F_o|^2(\text{mean}) | / \Sigma |F_o|^2$, $R1 = \Sigma | |F_o| - |F_c| | / \Sigma |F_o|$, $wR2 = \{ \Sigma w (|F_o|^2 - |F_c|^2)^2 / \Sigma |F_o|^2 \}^{1/2}$,

536 $S_{\text{fit}} = \{ \Sigma w (|F_o|^2 - |F_c|^2)^2 / (n - p) \}^{1/2}$, $w = 1 / \{ \sigma^2 (|F_o|^2) + (0.0389 \times P)^2 + 0.1365 \times P \}$ for new low-

537 density CaFe₂O₄-related, $w = 1 / \{\sigma^2 (|F_o|^2) + (0.0345 \times P)^2 + 2.1333 \times P\}$ for CaTi₂O₄-type synthesized
538 at 27 GPa, $w = 1 / \{\sigma^2 (|F_o|^2) + (0.0219 \times P)^2 + 5.4564 \times P\}$ for CaTi₂O₄-type synthesized at 45 GPa, and
539 $P = ([\text{Maximum} (|F_o|^2 \text{ or } 0)] + 2 \times |F_c|^2) / 3$, where F_o and F_c are the observed and calculated structure
540 factors, respectively. The w , n , and p are the statistical weight, the number of reflections, and the total
541 number of parameters refined, respectively. Maximum (F_o^2 or 0) is replaced by 0 when the observed F_o^2
542 value is negative, because the background is higher than the peak.

543 ^aSynthesized at 27 GPa and 2500 °C

544 ^bSynthesized at 45 GPa and 1727 °C

545 ^cUnique reflections with $F_o > 2\sigma$

Table 2a. Atomic coordinates and isotropic displacement parameters for new low-density CaFe₂O₄-related and CaTi₂O₄-type MgAl₂O₄

Atom	Wyckoff site	<i>x</i>	<i>y</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>U_{eq}</i>
New low-density CaFe₂O₄-related					
Mg	4 <i>c</i>	0.15912(10)	1/4	0.26908(9)	0.0078(3)
Al1	4 <i>c</i>	0.60877(8)	1/4	0.57273(8)	0.006767(3)
Al2	4 <i>c</i>	0.11274(8)	1/4	0.58543(8)	0.006767(3)
O1	4 <i>c</i>	0.2621(2)	1/4	0.47238(18)	0.006767(4)
O2	4 <i>c</i>	0.2044(2)	1/4	0.75060(17)	0.006767(4)
O3	4 <i>c</i>	0.0232(2)	1/4	0.10685(18)	0.006767(4)
O4	4 <i>c</i>	0.4887(2)	1/4	0.10292(18)	0.006767(5)
CaTi₂O₄-type synthesized at 27 GPa and 2500 °C					
Mg	4 <i>c</i>	0	0.11062(18)	1/4	0.0117(4)
Al	8 <i>f</i>	0	0.36577(9)	0.07277(10)	0.0063(2)
O1	4 <i>a</i>	0	0	0	0.0100(6)
O2	4 <i>c</i>	0	0.4524(3)	1/4	0.0093(6)
O3	8 <i>f</i>	0	0.2701(2)	0.6106(3)	0.0085(4)
CaTi₂O₄-type synthesized at 45 GPa and 1727 °C					
Mg	4 <i>c</i>	0	0.1122(3)	1/4	0.0070(7)
Al	8 <i>f</i>	0	0.3652(3)	0.0724(2)	0.0130(5)
O1	4 <i>a</i>	0	0	0	0.0159(14)
O2	4 <i>c</i>	0	0.4523(7)	1/4	0.0135(14)
O3	8 <i>f</i>	0	0.2695(5)	0.6108(5)	0.0139(10)

The equivalent displacement factor U_{eq} is calculated from $1/3[U_{11} (aa^*)^2 + U_{22} (bb^*)^2 + U_{33} (cc^*)^2 + 2U_{23} b^*c^*bc + 2U_{13} a^*c^*ac + 2U_{12} a^*b^*ab]$ (see Table 2b).

Table 2b. Anisotropic displacement parameters for new low-density CaFe_2O_4 -related and CaTi_2O_4 -type MgAl_2O_4

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
New low-density CaFe_2O_4-related						
Mg	0.0054(5)	0.0114(6)	0.0066(4)	0	0.0006(3)	0
Al1	0.0043(4)	0.0115(5)	0.0045(4)	0	0.0005(3)	0
Al2	0.0051(4)	0.0102(5)	0.0050(4)	0	-0.0004(3)	0
O1	0.0059(9)	0.0127(11)	0.0069(9)	0	-0.0003(6)	0
O2	0.0077(10)	0.0110(11)	0.0064(9)	0	0.0005(6)	0
O3	0.0064(8)	0.0112(12)	0.0060(9)	0	0.0014(7)	0
O4	0.0064(8)	0.0103(12)	0.0068(9)	0	-0.0001(7)	0
CaTi_2O_4-type synthesized at 27 GPa and 2500 °C						
Mg	0.0098(8)	0.0067(6)	0.0187(8)	0	0	0
Al	0.0067(4)	0.0038(4)	0.0084(4)	-0.0006(3)	0	0
O1	0.0094(14)	0.0073(12)	0.0131(14)	0.0012(10)	0	0
O2	0.0110(14)	0.0066(12)	0.0102(13)	0	0	0
O3	0.0085(10)	0.0059(8)	0.0111(9)	0.0002(7)	0	0
CaTi_2O_4-type synthesized at 45 GPa and 1727 °C						
Mg	0.0074(15)	0.0022(13)	0.0115(12)	0	0	0
Al	0.0136(10)	0.0124(9)	0.0130(8)	0.0011(8)	0	0

O1	0.017(3)	0.016(3)	0.015(3)	-0.003(3)	0	0
O2	0.014(3)	0.015(3)	0.011(3)	0	0	0
O3	0.017(3)	0.011(2)	0.014(2)	0.0026(17)	0	0

Notes: The anisotropic displacement factor exponent is $\exp\{-2\pi^2[h^2(a^*)^2U_{11} + k^2(b^*)^2U_{22} + l^2(c^*)^2U_{33} + 2klb^*c^*U_{23} + 2hla^*c^*U_{13} + 2hka^*b^*U_{12}]\}$.

Table 3. Interatomic distances and angles in new low-density CaFe₂O₄-related and CaTi₂O₄-type MgAl₂O₄

New low density CaFe₂O₄-related

Bond length (Å)

Mg–O1	2.195(2)	Al1–O1 ⁱⁱⁱ × 2	1.968(1)	Al2 ⁱ –O1 ⁱ	1.762(2)
Mg–O2 ⁱ × 2	1.970(1)	Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O2 ⁱ	1.933(2)	Al2 ⁱ –O2 ⁱ	1.817(2)
Mg–O3	2.016(2)	Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O3 ⁱⁱ × 2	1.963(1)	Al2 ⁱ –O4 × 2	1.780(1)
Mg–O4 ⁱⁱ	2.004(3)	Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O3 ⁱ	1.918(2)	Al2 ⁱ –O4 ⁱⁱⁱ	2.161(2)
Average	2.031	Average	1.952	Average	1.860
<i>n_c</i>	4.72	<i>n_c</i>	5.98	* ^V <i>n_c</i>	4.23
BVS	2.05	BVS	2.66	BVS	3.04
				* ^{IV} <i>n_c</i>	3.98
				* ^{IV} BVS	2.79

Bond angles (°)

O1–Mg–O4 ⁱⁱ	167.21(9)	O2 ⁱ –Mg–O2 ⁱ	99.7(1)	O2 ⁱ –Mg–O4 ⁱⁱ	123.81(6)
O1–Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O1	99.83(9)	O3 ⁱⁱ –Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O3 ⁱⁱ	100.18(9)	O3 ⁱ –Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O3 ⁱ	177.15(9)
O1 ⁱ –Al2 ⁱ –O4	117.99(6)	O4–Al2 ⁱ –O4	115.5(1)	O2 ⁱ –Al2 ⁱ –O4 ⁱⁱⁱ	175.78(9)
Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O3 ⁱ –Al1	95.73(7)	Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O1–Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ	99.83(9)	Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O3 ⁱⁱ –Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ	100.18(9)
Al2 ⁱ –O4 ⁱ –Al2 ⁱ	115.5(1)	Al1 ⁱⁱⁱ –O2 ⁱ –Al2 ⁱ	125.2(1)	Al1 ⁱⁱ –O2 ⁱ –Al2 ⁱ	127.66(6)

CaTi₂O₄-type synthesized at 27 GPa and 2500 °C

Bond length (Å)

Mg1–O1 × 2	2.5607(7)	Al1–O1 ⁱⁱⁱ × 2	1.9858(7)
Mg1–O2 ⁱ × 2	2.018(3)	Al1–O2	1.8468(17)
Mg1–O3 ⁱⁱ × 4	2.207(2)	Al1–O3 ⁱⁱ × 2	1.9076(16)

* ^{VI} Average	2.144	Al1–O3 ^{iv}	1.936(3)		
* ^{VIII} Average	2.248	Average	1.928		
* ^{VI} n_c	5.49	n_c	5.84		
* ^{VIII} n_c	5.89	BVS	2.86		
* ^{VI} BVS	1.83				
* ^{VIII} BVS	2.02				
Bond angles (°)					
O1–Al–O1	89.27(4)	O2–Al–O3	178.51(12)	O3–Al–O3	93.99(10)
O1–Al–O3	87.65(5)	Al–O2–Al	128.79(17)	Al–O3–Al	93.99(10)
Al–O1–Al	89.27(4)	O2–Mg–O2	87.49(13)	O3–Mg–O3	78.43(9)

CaTi₂O₄-type synthesized at 45 GPa and 1727 °C

Bond length (Å)

Mg1–O1 × 2	2.5797(12)	Al1–O1 ⁱⁱⁱ × 2	1.9953(19)
Mg1–O2 ⁱ × 2	2.036(6)	Al1–O2	1.861(4)
Mg1–O3 ⁱⁱ × 4	2.210(4)	Al1–O3 ⁱⁱ × 2	1.909(4)
* ^{VI} Average	2.152	Al1–O3 ^{iv}	1.944(6)
* ^{VIII} Average	2.259	Average	1.936
* ^{VI} n_c	5.74	n_c	5.84
* ^{VIII} n_c	5.98	BVS	2.80
* ^{VI} BVS	1.78		
* ^{VIII} BVS	1.96		

Bond angles (°)

O1–Al–O1	89.05(11)	O2–Al–O3	178.6(3)	O3–Al–O3	94.3(3)
O1–Al–O3	87.67(11)	Al–O2–Al	128.7(4)	Al–O3–Al	97.4(2)

Al-O1-Al	90.95(11)	O2-Mg-O2	86.8(3)	O3-Mg-O3	78.55(17)
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Abbreviations: n_c : effective coordination number; BVS: bond valence sum value.

*IV, V, VI, and VIII indicate these values were calculated using the four, five, six, and eight nearest neighbor oxygen-cation bonds, respectively.

Table 4. Molar volumes and densities of phases with MgAl₂O₄ composition

Phase	V_m (cm ³ /mol)	ρ (g/cm ³)	Reference
New low-density CaFe ₂ O ₄ -related	40.66(1)	3.499(1)	This study
Sp	39.760(3)	3.578(1)	[1]
MgO Pc + Al ₂ O ₃ Cor	36.853(5)	3.860(1)	[2], [3]
1/2(mLd-type Mg ₂ Al ₂ O ₅ + Al ₂ O ₃ Cor)	36.809(3)	3.865(1)	[4]
CF-type	36.136(3)	3.937(1)	[5]
	36.17(2)	3.933(1)	This study
CT-type	36.368(8)	3.912(1)	*This study
	36.82(8)	3.864(1)	†This study
	36.23(2)	3.927(3)	[6]

Abbreviations: Sp: spinel; Pc: periclase; Cor: corundum; mLd: modified ludwigite; CF: calcium ferrite; CT: calcium titanate.

[1] Meducin et al. (2004); [2] Toebbens et al. (2001); [3] Tsirelson et al. (1998); [4] Enomoto et al. (2009); [5] Kojitani et al. (2007); and [6] Ono et al. (2006)

*Synthesized at 27 GPa and 2500 °C

†Synthesized at 45 GPa and 1727 °C